

Supplementary Information – Methodology of Evaluating the Activation Energy of Oxygen Reduction Reaction on Pt-based Electrodes

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Contents

S1 Equilibrium potentials of ORR	2
S2 Tafel plots of ORR in 0.1M HClO ₄	6
S3 Partial oxidation current density	7
S4 Dissociative path of ORR.....	8
S5 Generalization of the methodology for alternative RDS scenarios.....	11
S6 The derivative of general kinetic equation with respect to the reciprocal temperature	12
S7 Literature	13

S1 Equilibrium potentials of ORR

The derivation is based on the Nernst equation, **Eq. S1**, as formulated for the reaction in the form of **Eq. 6** or **Eq. 7**, respectively.

$$E_{\text{ORR,l/g,T}} = E_{\text{ORR,l/g,T}}^{\circ} - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{a_{\text{H}_2\text{O,l/g}}^2}{a_{\text{O}_2,\text{g}} a_{\text{H}^+,\text{aq}}^4} \quad \text{Eq. S1}$$

The activity of reacting O₂ ($a_{\text{O}_2,\text{g}}$) can be calculated from partial pressure of O₂, $p_{\text{O}_2,T}$, and standard pressure, p_{st} , using **Eq. S2**,

$$a_{\text{O}_2,T} = \varphi_{\text{O}_2} \frac{p_{\text{O}_2,T}}{p_{\text{st}}} \quad \text{Eq. S2}$$

where the fugacity coefficient $\varphi_{\text{O}_2} \approx 1$ can be considered in the context of the high temperatures and ambient pressure p used (in this case $p \approx p_{\text{st}}$, measurements were carried out under atmospheric pressure). Subscript “g” in the activity term $a_{\text{O}_2,\text{g}}$ denotes application of standard state of ideal gas. As the vapours above H₃PO₄ solutions up to a temperature of about 320°C contain practically only H₂O [1-3] (at higher temperatures phosphorous(V) oxide is found in the gas phase as well), pure O₂ brought to the system under these conditions will get saturated only with H₂O vapour. The same is valid for 0.1M HClO₄. Therefore, $p_{\text{O}_2,T}$ in both systems can be expressed using **Eq. S3**,

$$p_{\text{O}_2,T} = p - p_{\text{H}_2\text{O},T} \quad \text{Eq. S3}$$

$p_{\text{O}_2,T}$ values for temperatures of 5-60°C for 0.1M HClO₄ are summarised in **Table S3**, $p_{\text{O}_2,T}$ values for temperatures of 120-180°C and H₃PO₄ concentrations of 97.6 wt.% (i.e., 70.9 wt.% P₄O₁₀) are summarised in **Table S4** (H₂O vapour pressure data above H₃PO₄ were taken from [1, 3], H₂O vapour pressure data above pure H₂O were taken from [4]).

Table S1: Standard redox potentials for ORR (E_{ORR}°) considering the formation of H₂O in the liquid state (5-60°C)

$t / ^{\circ}\text{C}$	$E_{\text{ORR,l,T}}^{\circ} / \text{V}$
5	1.2458
10	1.2416
15	1.2373
20	1.2331
25	1.2289
30	1.2246
35	1.2204
40	1.2162
45	1.2119

50	1.2077
55	1.2035
60	1.1992

Table S2: Standard redox potentials for ORR (E_{ORR}°) considering the formation of H_2O the liquid (l) and gaseous (g) state (120-180°C)

$t / ^{\circ}C$	$E_{ORR,l,T}^{\circ} / V$	$E_{ORR,g,T}^{\circ} / V$
120	1.148	1.163
140	1.131	1.158
160	1.115	1.153
180	1.098	1.149

Table S3: Relevant values of reaction species in 0.1M $HClO_4$ at different temperatures for $E_{ORR,T}$ calculation

$t / ^{\circ}C$	$p_{H_2O} = p_{H_2O}^* / Pa$ [4]	$a_{O_2,g}$	$a_{H_2O,l} \sim x_{H_2O,l}$	$a_{H^+,aq}$	$c_{O_2} / mmol\ dm^{-3}$
5	873	0.9913	≈ 1	0.1633	1.84
10	1228	0.9879	1	0.1401	1.63
15	1706	0.9832	1	0.1193	1.46
20	2339	0.9769	1	0.1102	1.31
25	3169	0.9687	1	0.1103	1.20
30	4246	0.9581	1	0.1091	1.10
35	5627	0.9445	1	0.1102	1.01
40	7381	0.9272	1	0.1099	0.93
45	9590	0.9054	1	0.1084	0.86
50	12344	0.8782	1	0.1069	0.80
55	15752	0.8445	1	0.1074	0.74
60	19932	0.8033	1	0.1067	0.68

Table S4: Relevant values of reaction species in 97.6 wt.% H_3PO_4 at different temperatures for $E_{ORR,T}$ calculation

$t / ^{\circ}C$	p_{H_2O} / kPa [1, 3]	$p_{H_2O}^* / kPa$ [4]	$a_{O_2,g}$	$a_{H_2O,g}$	$a_{H_2O,l}$	$a_{H^+,aq}$
120	5.687	198.670	0.944	0.056	0.029	≈ 0.010
140	12.473	361.540	0.877	0.123	0.034	0.010
160	25.441	618.230	0.749	0.251	0.041	0.010

Determining the proton activity $a_{\text{H}^+, \text{aq}}$ in the case of an aqueous HClO_4 is straightforward, as it can be relatively well estimated directly from the measured pH values (**Table S3**). Much more difficult is a determination of $a_{\text{H}^+, \text{aq}}$ in the case of hot and conc. H_3PO_4 . The only value mentioned in the literature is the one for 97.6 wt.% H_3PO_4 at temperature 150°C ($a_{\text{H}^+, \text{aq}} = 0.0102$) [5]. Therefore, due the absence of other data, this value was used for all temperatures within an interval of $120\text{-}180^\circ\text{C}$. It must be stressed that this will necessarily lead to error whose extent is impossible to assess.

The H_2O activity $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{l}}$ in the 0.1M HClO_4 can be considered equal to unity. In the case of conc. H_3PO_4 , for the reaction of **Eq. 6** and **Eq. 7**, it is necessary to consider the different expressions for the H_2O activities, i.e. $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{l}}$ and $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{g}}$ for substituting into **Eq. S1**. In the case of H_2O vapour, its activity, $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{g}}$, can be calculated as the ratio of $p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, T}$ to $p_{\text{st.}}$, see **Eq. S4**,

$$a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{g}} = \varphi_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \frac{p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, T}}{p_{\text{st.}}} \quad \text{Eq. S4}$$

where $\varphi_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ represents fugacity coefficient of H_2O . In the context of the elevated temperatures and ambient pressure, it can be assumed that $\varphi_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \approx 1$. If the reaction is considered to produce liquid H_2O , $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{l}}$ is equal to the ratio of $p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, T}$ to the vapour pressure of pure H_2O at a given temperature ($p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, T}^*$) (given in **Table S3-4**) according to **Eq. S5**.

$$a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{l}} = \frac{p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, T}}{p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, T}^*} \quad \text{Eq. S5}$$

Another possibility of determining the $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{l}}$ would be using **Eq. S6** based on the concentration of H_2O , $c_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, and the activity coefficient of H_2O in H_3PO_4 at a given temperature, $\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, according to **Eq. S6**.

$$a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{l}} = \gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \frac{c_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{c_{\text{st.}}} \quad \text{Eq. S6}$$

However, activity coefficient data are not available in the literature and in the context of a strong chemical interaction between H_2O and (poly)phosphoric acids involving complicated chemical equilibria, the application of the standard state based on an infinitely diluted solution of H_2O in H_3PO_4 seems obscure.

To sum up, the calculated $E_{\text{ORR}, T}$ values for 0.1M HClO_4 at $5\text{-}65^\circ\text{C}$ and for 97.6 wt.% H_3PO_4 at $120\text{-}180^\circ\text{C}$ are summarised in **Table S5** and **Table S6**, resp.

Table S5: Equilibrium potentials for ORR in 0.1M HClO₄ at temperatures of 5-60°C, for liquid H₂O as a product consideration of changes in the activities of the species involved.

$t / ^\circ\text{C}$	$E_{\text{ORR},l,T} / \text{V}$	$T / ^\circ\text{C}$	$E_{\text{ORR},l,T} / \text{V}$
5	1.2023	35	1.1615
10	1.1955	40	1.1561
15	1.1864	45	1.1503
20	1.1772	50	1.1445
25	1.1716	55	1.1392
30	1.1665	60	1.1334

Table S6: Equilibrium potentials for ORR in 97.6 wt.% H₃PO₄ at temperatures of 120-180°C, for liquid or gaseous H₂O as a product, consideration of changes in the activities of the species involved.

$t / ^\circ\text{C}$	$E_{\text{ORR},g,T} / \text{V}$	$E_{\text{ORR},l,T} / \text{V}$
120	1.056	1.053
140	1.031	1.027
160	1.005	1.000
180	0.978	0.971

S2 Tafel plots of ORR in 0.1M HClO₄

Figure S1-S12: LSVs measured at Pt-RDE using revolution rates 900 rpm; 0.1M HClO₄, 10 mV s⁻¹, temperatures of 5-60 °C, corrected for background currents and uncompensated resistance, use of corresponding $E_{\text{ORR,L,T}}$ (section S1)

S3 Partial oxidation current density

Analogously to Eq. 21-22, the partial oxidation current density j_{OX} , i.e. the first term on the right side of Eq. 20 can be expressed as Eq. S7.

$$j_{\text{ex}} = j_{\text{ox}}$$

$$= 4Fk_{\text{as}}^{\circ} \frac{a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 c_{\text{st}}^3 c_{\text{O}}}{c_{\text{H}^+}^3} e^{\frac{3F \left(\frac{-RT}{4F} \ln \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5 \frac{c_{\text{O}}}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+} c_{\text{st}}^*} + (E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_3^{\circ'}) \right)}{RT}} (1-\beta) F \left(\frac{-RT}{4F} \ln \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5 \frac{c_{\text{O}}}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+} c_{\text{st}}^*} + (E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_2^{\circ'}) \right)}$$

Eq. S7

After rearrangement, the **Eq. S8** is obtained.

$$j_{\text{ex}} = 4Fk_{\text{as}}^{\circ} \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 c_{\text{st}}^3 c_{\text{O}}}{c_{\text{H}^+}^3} e^{-\frac{3}{4} \ln \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+} c_{\text{st}}^*}} e^{\frac{3F(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_3^{\circ'})}{RT}} e^{-\frac{(1-\beta)}{4} \ln \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+} c_{\text{st}}^*}} e^{\frac{(1-\beta)F(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_2^{\circ'})}{RT}}$$

$$j_{\text{ex}} = 4Fk_{\text{as}}^{\circ} c_{\text{H}^+}^{-3+3+1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{\frac{3}{4}+\frac{1}{4}-\frac{\beta}{4}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{2-\frac{3}{2}-\frac{1}{2}+\frac{\beta}{2}} c_{\text{O}}^{\frac{3}{4}-\frac{15}{4}-\frac{5}{4}+\frac{5\beta}{4}} e^{\frac{3F(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_3^{\circ'})}{RT}} e^{\frac{(1-\beta)F(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_2^{\circ'})}{RT}}$$

$$j_{\text{ex}} = 4Fk_{\text{as}}^{\circ} c_{\text{H}^+}^{1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{1-\frac{\beta}{4}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 c_{\text{O}}^{\frac{\beta}{4}} c_{\text{st}}^{\frac{-2+5\beta}{4}} \left\{ e^{\frac{3F(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_3^{\circ'}) + (1-\beta)F(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_2^{\circ'})}{RT}} \right\} \quad \text{Eq. S8}$$

S4 Dissociative path of ORR

When the **dissociative path** of the ORR is considered to take place, the overall reaction is:

The dissociative adsorption of O_2 leads to two O^* adsorbed on the Pt surface (**Eq. S10**).

Subsequently, the two adsorbed O^* undergo one-electron reductions forming adsorbed OH^* in two parallel RDSs (**Eq. S11**). In other words, this RDS has to occur two times in the reaction sequence.

Consequently, each OH^* formed in one RDS undergoes one electron reduction connected with protonation, see **Eq. S12**.

The overall current density is proportional to the current density of the two RDS steps (**Eq. S11**), j_{RDS} , expressed by the kinetic equation (**Eq. S13**)

$$j = 2j_{\text{RDS}} = 4F\bar{k}_{\text{dis}} c_{\text{OH}^*} e^{\frac{(1-\beta)F(E - E_4^{\circ'})}{RT}} - 4F\vec{k}_{\text{dis}} c_{\text{O}^*} c_{\text{H}^+} e^{\frac{-\beta F(E - E_4^{\circ'})}{RT}} \quad \text{Eq. S13}$$

where $E_4^{\circ'}$ is formal potential of the RDS, i.e. **Eq. S11**, c_{x^*} represent the surface concentrations of individual adsorbed species and the subscript "dis" in k_{dis} indicates the dissociative O_2 adsorption pathway. Assuming chemical equilibrium in step (**Eq. S10**) preceding RDS, the equilibrium adsorption constant K_2 can be expressed as **Eq. S14**,

$$K_2 = \frac{a_{O^*}^2}{a_{O_2} a_{\ominus}^2} = \frac{\gamma_{O^*}^2 c_{O^*}^2 c_{st.} c_{st.}^2}{\gamma_{O_2} c_{O_2} \gamma_{\ominus}^2 c_{\ominus}^2 c_{st.}^2} \quad \text{Eq. S14}$$

and when considering activity coefficients $\gamma_x = 1$, c_{O^*} can be obtained using **Eq. S15**,

$$K_2' = \frac{c_{O^*}^2 c_{st.}}{c_{O_2} c_{\ominus}^2}$$

$$c_{O^*} = \sqrt{\frac{K_2' c_{O_2} c_{\ominus}^2}{c_{st.}}} \quad \text{Eq. S15}$$

where K_2' is dimensionless apparent equilibrium constant. Analogously, the derivation of the c_{OOH^*} is based on assuming pseudo-equilibrium in the steps after RDS, i.e. **Eq. S12** by means of Nernst equation (**Eq. S16**).

$$E_5 = E_5^\circ - \frac{RT}{F} \ln \left(\frac{a_{H_2O,1} a_{\ominus}}{a_{H^+} a_{OH^*}} \right) \quad \text{Eq. S16}$$

Rearrangement provides the desired result **Eq. S17**. The standard state used for the adsorbed species is based on recommendations provided in [6]).

$$E_5 = E_5^\circ - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \left(\frac{x_{H_2O} \cdot \frac{c_{\ominus}}{c_{st.}}}{\frac{c_{H^+}}{c_{st.}} \cdot \frac{c_{OH^*}}{c_{st.}}} \right) - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \left(\frac{\gamma_{H_2O,1} \gamma_{\ominus}}{\gamma_{H^+} \gamma_{OH^*}} \right)$$

$$E_5 = E_5^{\circ'} - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \left(\frac{x_{H_2O} \cdot \frac{c_{\ominus}}{c_{st.}}}{\frac{c_{H^+}}{c_{st.}} \cdot \frac{c_{OH^*}}{c_{st.}}} \right)$$

$$c_{OH^*} = \frac{x_{H_2O} c_{st.} c_{\ominus}}{c_{H^+}} e^{\frac{F(E_5 - E_5^{\circ'})}{RT}} \quad \text{Eq. S17}$$

After substituting the relations **Eq. S15** and **Eq. S17** into **Eq. S13**, the overall kinetic equation **Eq. S18** of the reaction **Eq. S9** is obtained.

$$j = 4F \bar{k}_{dis} \frac{x_{H_2O} c_{st.} c_{\ominus}}{c_{H^+}} e^{\frac{F(E_5 - E_5^{\circ'})}{RT}} \frac{(1-\beta) F(E - E_4^{\circ'})}{RT} - 4F \vec{k}_{dis} \frac{c_{\ominus} c_{H^+} \sqrt{K_1' c_{O_2}}}{\sqrt{c_{st.}}} e^{\frac{-\beta F(E - E_4^{\circ'})}{RT}}$$

Eq. S18

Since the reference potential in **Eq. S13** is formal potential $E_4^{\circ'}$ of reaction **Eq. S11**, it applies that $\bar{k}_{dis} = \vec{k}_{dis} = k_{dis}^\circ$. If it is moreover considered that step in **Eq. S11** represents RDS, it becomes obvious that this k_{dis}° value should be used in determining ΔG^\ddagger of the whole ORR process, i.e. the purpose of following derivation is to find dependence $k_{dis}^\circ = f(j_{ex}, c_{H^+}, c_{O_2}, x_{H_2O})$.

Having analytical expression for current density of the overall ORR (**Eq. S18**) allows to investigate also the corresponding exchange current density, j_{ex} . This can be done by setting the electrode potential E equal to E_{ORR} from Nernst equation for overall ORR process (**Eq. S1**).

Noting that this corresponds to state with $j = 0$ and consequently $j_{\text{ex}} = -j_{\text{red}} = j_{\text{ox}}$, where j_{ox} and j_{red} correspond to the first and second term on the right side of the **Eq. S18** and are called partial oxidation and partial reduction current density, respectively. For j_{red} , below **Eq. S19** can be obtained.

$$-j_{\text{ex}} = j_{\text{red}} = -4F\vec{k}_{\text{dis}} \frac{c_{\ominus} c_{\text{H}^+} \sqrt{K'_2 c_{\text{O}_2}}}{\sqrt{c_{\text{st}}}} e^{\frac{-\beta F \left(\frac{-RT}{4F} \ln \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+}^4} + (E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_4) \right)}{RT}} \quad \text{Eq. S19}$$

After rearrangement, the **Eq. S20** is obtained.

$$-j_{\text{ex}} = -4Fk^{\circ}_{\text{dis}} c_{\text{H}^+}^{1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{\frac{1-\beta}{4}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 c_{\ominus} c_{\text{st}}^{\frac{-3+5\beta}{2} + \frac{\beta}{4}} \left\{ \sqrt{K'_2} e^{\frac{-\beta F (E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_4)}{RT}} \right\} \quad \text{Eq. S20} = \text{Eq. 26}$$

Analogously to the above treatment of j_{red} , the development of the partial oxidation current density j_{ox} , i.e. the first term on the right side of **Eq. S18** yields the very same dependence of j_{ex} on composition of the system. For j_{ox} , below **Eq. S21** can be obtained.

$$j_{\text{ex}} = j_{\text{ox}} = 4F\vec{k}_{\text{dis}} \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} c_{\text{st}} c_{\ominus}}{c_{\text{H}^+}} e^{\frac{F \left(\frac{-RT}{4F} \ln \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+}^4} + (E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_5) \right)}{RT}} e^{\frac{(1-\beta) F \left(\frac{-RT}{4F} \ln \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+}^4} + (E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_4) \right)}{RT}}$$

Eq. S21

After rearrangement, the **Eq. S22** is obtained.

$$j_{\text{ex}} = 4Fk^{\circ}_{\text{dis}} \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} c_{\text{st}} c_{\ominus}}{c_{\text{H}^+}} e^{-\frac{1}{4} \ln \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+}^4}} e^{\frac{F(E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_5)}{RT}} e^{-\frac{(1-\beta) x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5}{4 c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+}^4}} e^{\frac{(1-\beta) F (E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_4)}{RT}}$$

$$j_{\text{ex}} = 4Fk^{\circ}_{\text{dis}} c_{\text{H}^+}^{-1+1+1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{4} - \frac{\beta}{4}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{1 - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{\beta}{2}} c_{\ominus} c_{\text{st}}^{1 - \frac{5}{4} - \frac{5}{4} + \frac{5\beta}{4}} e^{\frac{F(E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_5)}{RT}} e^{\frac{(1-\beta) F (E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_4)}{RT}}$$

$$j_{\text{ex}} = 4Fk^{\circ}_{\text{dis}} c_{\text{H}^+}^{1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{\frac{1-\beta}{4}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 c_{\ominus} c_{\text{st}}^{\frac{-3+5\beta}{2} + \frac{\beta}{4}} \left\{ e^{\frac{F(E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_5) + (1-\beta) F (E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_4)}{RT}} \right\} \quad \text{Eq. S22}$$

Considering that c_{\ominus} (in **Eq. S20** and **Eq. S22**) must be the same for both partial current density notations, j_{ox} and j_{red} differ (except for the sign) only by notation of constant terms. In particular, comparison of **Eq. S20** and **Eq. S22** yields **Eq. S23**, where the differences between E'_4 and E'_5 , K'_2 and E'_{ORR} stand out.

$$e^{\frac{F(E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_5) + F(E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_4)}{RT}} = \sqrt{K'_2} \quad \text{Eq. S23}$$

After taking logarithm of **Eq. S23**, equality **Eq. S24** can be obtained,

$$-4FE'_{\text{ORR}} = -2FE'_4 - 2FE'_5 - RT \ln K'_2$$

$$-4FE^{\circ}_{\text{ORR}} - RT \ln \frac{\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+} \gamma_{\text{O}_2}} = -2FE^{\circ}_4 - 2FE^{\circ}_5 - RT \ln K_2 - RT \ln \frac{\gamma_{\text{O}^{\circ 2}}}{\gamma_{\text{O}_2} \gamma_{\text{O}^{\circ}}} - RT \ln \frac{\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 \gamma_{\text{O}^{\circ}}}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+}^4 \gamma_{\text{O}^{\circ 2}}}$$

$$\Delta G^{\circ}_{\text{ORR}} = \Delta G^{\circ}_2 + \Delta G^{\circ}_3 + \Delta G^{\circ}_1 \quad \text{Eq. S24}$$

which is consistent with Hess' law of the thermodynamic cycle supporting validity of the whole treatment (in Eq. S11 2 e⁻ are accepted, in Eq. S12 2 e⁻ are accepted, in the total reaction Eq. S9 then 4 e⁻). By excluding the mostly unknown constant terms (curly brackets) in Eq. S18 or Eq. S22, the desired relation between k°_{dis} and experimentally determined j_{ex} value valid at given temperature is obtained, see Eq. S25. The only parameter, which is not easily available, is c_{\ominus} . It is important to mention that using Eq. S25 only relative changes of the k°_{dis} could be obtained.

$$k^{\circ}_{\text{dis}} \propto \frac{j_{\text{ex}}}{c_{\text{H}^+}^{1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{\frac{1-\beta}{2}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\frac{\beta}{2}} c_{\ominus}} \quad \text{Eq. S25 = Eq. 27}$$

However, if j_{ex} values are determined at various temperatures, variation of all parameters in Eq. S20 or Eq. S22 must be considered (recall that the c_{H^+} in case of conc. H₃PO₄ was assumed constant due to lack of data). It is obvious that values such as c_{\ominus} , K'_2 and term $(E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_4)/RT$ or $(E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_5)/RT$ are not easy to obtain and one is left with simplifying assumption that they do not vary significantly with temperature. For K'_2 it can be assumed that its value should decrease with increasing temperature, while for c_{\ominus} its value should increase, so it is possible that these effects will be compensated. Due to lack of data, in case of conc. H₃PO₄ it was assumed that the molar ratio of H₂O in H₃PO₄ $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ can be approximated the $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O},1}$ defined by Eq. S5.

S5 Generalization of the methodology for alternative RDS scenarios

The analysis presented in the main text is based on the assumption that the one-electron reduction of adsorbed O₂* to OOH* (Eq. 13) represents the RDS in the associative ORR pathway. However, the RDS may change depending on operational conditions such as temperature, pH, or electrolyte composition. In particular, under high-temperature conditions in phosphoric acid (Section 3.4), the charge transfer coefficient α increases significantly (though this change can have other reasons, such as changes in surface coverage by particular intermediate), which renders the assumption of a single, constant RDS questionable.

To illustrate the broader applicability of the approach, the following section demonstrates the main principles, how the methodology can be adapted to accommodate alternative RDS scenarios. Although the specific kinetic expressions will differ depending on the nature of the RDS, the general structure of the derivation remains consistent. This approach necessitates knowledge of mechanism of both the elementary steps preceding the RDS and RDS itself. Steps following the RDS can be incorporated into “an overall post-RDS reaction”.

In ideal case, all preceding equilibria (including their temperature dependence) should be known, i.e. electrochemical steps are treated via the Nernst equation with appropriate formal potentials and chemical/adsorption steps are described through corresponding equilibria with equilibrium constants. Similarly, equilibria for the overall post-RDS reaction should be known. Concentrations of reaction intermediates (and their temperature dependencies) are not required. It is sufficient to know concentrations of products and reactants of the overall reaction process including surface concentration of free adsorption sites. The RDS rate is then expressed using a rate law: for electrochemical processes, this corresponds to a Butler–Volmer-type expression; for chemical steps, it is described by a conventional kinetic rate law of elementary reaction. Reactant concentrations in the RDS can be derived from pre-equilibria. Similarly, the concentrations of RDS products can be related to the equilibrium of the overall post-RDS reaction.

The summary of quantities required is presented in **Table S7**:

Table S7: Necessary quantities for deriving the dependence of $k = f(j_{ex}, c_x)$, $K_{(T)}$ equilibrium constant, $E_{(T)}^{\circ}$ formal potential, “Mechanism” = mechanism of elementary reaction step(s), $c(T)$ represents temperature-dependent concentration of components

	Mechanism	$K_{(T)}$ or $E_{(T)}^{\circ}$	$c(T)$
Steps before RDS	×	✓	Overall reaction reactants and products including free adsorption sites
RDS	✓	✓	
Overall post-RDS reaction	×	✓	

S6 The derivative of general kinetic equation with respect to the reciprocal temperature

General kinetic equation (**Eq. S26**), with assumption $\eta \gg 0$, constant pressure and $\alpha \neq f(T)$,

$$j_k = kFc_i^{f(\alpha)} e^{\frac{\alpha F\eta}{RT}} \quad \text{Eq. S26}$$

after logarithmisation (**Eq. S27**),

$$\ln j_k = \ln k + \ln F + \sum_{i=1}^n f(\alpha) \ln c_i + \frac{\alpha F\eta}{RT} \quad \text{Eq. S27}$$

can be differentiated respect to reciprocal temperature $1/T$, **Eq. S28** (concentration of reactants/products/adsorbed intermediates $c_i = f(T)$ and reaction rate constant $k = f(T)$),

$$d \ln j_k = \frac{1}{k} \frac{\partial k}{\partial \frac{1}{T}} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f(\alpha)}{c_i} \frac{\partial c_i}{\partial \frac{1}{T}} + \frac{\alpha F\eta}{R} \quad \text{Eq. S28}$$

and considering the Arrhenius equation (**Eq. 1**), yields **Eq. S29**.

$$\frac{d \ln j_k}{d \frac{1}{T}} = \frac{-\Delta G_k^\ddagger}{R} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f(\alpha)}{c_i} \frac{\partial c_i}{\partial \frac{1}{T}} + \frac{\alpha F\eta}{R} \quad \text{Eq. S29}$$

This expression easily shows that the derivative $\frac{d \ln j_k}{d \frac{1}{T}}$ is generally not equal just to $\frac{-\Delta G^\ddagger}{R}$, but also contains additional concentration term that can vary with T , $\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f(\alpha)}{c_i} \frac{\partial c_i}{\partial \frac{1}{T}}$ and it is also affected by value of overpotential η selected for analysis.

S7 Literature

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